

OPERA ART IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article talks about Opera art as well as Mustafa Bafojev's opera "The Sky of Love".

Key word: Opera, creators, artist, composer, scene, genre, national heritage.

ОПЕРНОЕ ИСКУССТВО В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится об оперном искусстве, а также об опере Мустафы Бафоева «Небо любви».

Ключевые слова: Опера, создатели, художник, композитор, сцена, жанр, национальное наследие.

Opera is a complex genre that requires the harmony of various arts and, especially, requires the composer to have a thorough knowledge of the features of the scene and the laws of dramaturgy. Therefore, it is clear from history that even recognized genius composers (K.V. Gluck, R. Wagner, J. Verdi, P. Tchaikovsky, etc.) could not create their classic operas on the first attempt. According to observations, the creators were able to succeed in this field due to the necessary experience and professional skills they gained as a result of many researches in the field of opera. The opera "Sevgim samosi"⁴⁵, created by the artist of Uzbekistan, composer Mustafa Bafojev based on the libretto of the national poet of Uzbekistan Jumanyoz Jabbarov, attracts attention with a number of aspects. First of all, it is permissible to dwell on the "necessary experience and qualification" mentioned above. Until the opera "Sevgim samosi", we witness how M. Bafojev mastered stage rules step by step during bold research. At first, he tried his hand at musical dramas (Seventh Demon, Broken Strings, etc.) similar to opera. He created the opera "Umar Khayyom" in 1987, relying on the creative results of QoM. After that, the author continued his research on stage music and the creation of a historical figure in it in a new section, and during 1991-1995, he presented the TV ballets "Nadira", "Ulugbek Burji" and "Light from Moziydan Nur" to the judgment of the audience. As a result of this research, the tele-opera "Bukhoroi Sharif" was created.

And, finally, on May 2, 2008, the premiere of the opera "Sevgim Samosi" about the life of a historical person, our compatriot Ahmed Fargani, took place. The dramaturgy of this opera,

which consists of two acts and five scenes, is based on the comparison and "clash" of different styles.

45 The opera was called "Ahmad al-Farghani" in the first version.

In this case, musical samples re-expressed on the basis of the national heritage are of prime importance in the development of events.

Summary of the opera 1 act

View 1. Young Ahmed Farghani goes on a trip to Baghdad, the center of knowledge of the East, in search of enlightenment. On the way, he experienced many hardships. After arriving in Baghdad, along with homesickness, he is filled with complex thoughts about whether the path he has chosen is the right one. Young Ahmad, engrossed in imagination, attracts the attention of the famous scholar al-Khorazmi, who was walking in the garden with his students nearby. The scholar who invited the young man to talk knows his thirst for knowledge and gives him many useful tips on this path. Ahmed's joy, recognizing his compatriot in the face of Alloma, is boundless. View 2. People gathered in a large square in Baghdad to celebrate Ramadan. The gathered people are praising the Creator. Famous scientists and religious figures are also seen on the square. Al-Khorazmi introduced his student Ahmad to the great scholars of that time and pointed to Ibn Yusuf, who did not achieve results in any field of science. At that moment, King Mamun comes in and congratulates the people on the holiday. The king's attention falls on the young man standing next to al-Khorazmi. Shah Ma'mun, knowing the intention of young Ahmed to engage in science, asked the scientists to examine him in the field of exact and religious sciences. Everyone is surprised by the wise answers of Khorezmi's student. Only Ibn Yusuf, seeing his opponent in the form of young Ahmed, is displeased. A young man and a young woman who are masters of words appear on the square and invite everyone to join. At that moment, Ahmed catches the eye of the beautiful and popular Safina among the girls, and immediately falls in love with him.

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